

Some common weed hosts of *Sarocladium oryzae* in Assam, India

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We observed severe sheath rot (ShR) symptoms on the common wetland weed, *Oryza rufipogon*, during a 1990 field survey in Jorhat district of Assam. We identified the causal organism to be *Sarocladium oryzae*, the incitant of rice ShR. The isolate reproduced the typical symptom on *O. rufipogon* and was found pathogenic to rice.

We carried out a pathogenicity test on 10 common ricefield weeds during the 1991 wet season to investigate the role of collateral hosts in perpetuating the pathogen. We inoculated weeds with an isolate from susceptible rice cultivar IR50 either by inserting an inoculum-

containing rice grain inside the uppermost leaf sheath or by spraying suspension after slightly injuring the plant (used where insertion of a grain was difficult).

Of the 10 weeds tested (see table), seven were successfully infected by the isolate. The remaining three did not exhibit any susceptible reaction even after repeated inoculations.

E. colona and *O. rufipogon* were the most susceptible because they produced symptoms the earliest (see table).

Pathogenicity tests using the fungus isolated from the artificially infected weeds gave positive results on IR50. A cross-inoculation test among the seven susceptible weeds with the pathogen was also successful with the symptoms being similar to those that develop when inoculated by rice isolates. These results, along with microscopic observation of the pathogen, confirmed the identity of *S. oryzae*. The results show that

Pathogenicity of *Sarocladium oryzae* on some weeds commonly found near ricefields.

Weed	Reaction ^a	Appearance of initial symptom (h after inoculation)
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	+	72
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Bum. f.) Presl.	+	120
<i>Hymenachne assamica</i> (Hook f.) Hitchc.	+	168
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Swartz.	+	144
<i>Panicum walense</i> Mez.	+	144
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i> Griff.	+	72
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	+	96
<i>Axonopus compressus</i> (Swartz.) Beauv.	-	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	-	
<i>Panicum notatum</i> Retz.	-	

^a+ = symptom appeared upon inoculation, - = did not appear upon inoculation.

H. assamica, *L. hexandra*, *P. walense*, and *O. rufipogon* are new weed hosts of the pathogen. □

Rice tungro disease (RTD) incidence in Assam, India

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RTD was first noticed in 1990 in about 100 ha of winter rice (Jul-Dec) in Kamrup and Nalbari districts. The incidence was moderate to severe, depending upon variety. Mashuri and a few traditional winter rice cultivars were severely affected. There had been no confirmed report of RTD in Assam up until then, although it

had probably been mistaken for Fe-induced yellowing, which is a major problem in the region.

An iodine test was used to narrow down the probable causes of yellowing. The veins of RTD-infected leaves turned black when dipped in tincture of iodine solution (1:4). Leaves with yellowing symptoms due to Fe toxicity did not turn black.

We conducted transmission tests of RTD samples collected from different sites to confirm the virus. About 50 viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* were confined to each sample for 48 h and then kept on 10-d-old healthy TN1 seedlings, at

2 insects/seedling, for 24 h. Typical symptoms of RTD developed after 10-15 d.

Leaf samples of selected disease isolates from TN1 were collected 30 d after incubation and homogenized with 0.02 M phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4). The extracts were indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using antisera obtained from IRRI. All of the isolates showed positive reaction to antisera of rice tungro bacilliform virus and rice tungro spherical virus, indicating that the samples were infected with both. This is the first confirmed report of RTD from this region. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Rice leaffolder (LF) outbreak in valleys of Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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Cnaphalocrocis medinalis Guenée has become a serious rice pest under both irrigated transplanted and upland conditions in the hills of UP. During 1991 kharif (monsoon), a severe LF outbreak occurred in the irrigated valley regions of Almora district. We conducted an extensive survey during the cropping season to determine LF incidence.

In each of the surveyed valleys, we selected at random five ricefields of each variety and made observations at five randomly selected 1 m²-spots in each field. The plants in each spot were thoroughly screened for insects. We computed the ratio of infested plants to the number of plants sampled. The larvae collected from infested fields

Percent of leaves damaged by LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on different rice varieties in valleys of the hilly regions of UP, India, 1991 kharif.

Valley	Variety	Av leaf damage (%)
Gagas Valley (1,100 m asl) ^a	Govind	85
	Pant Dhan 6	72
	VL-16	80
	Local	55
Garur Valley (1,200 m asl)	Govind	86
	VL-16	85
	VLK39	78
	Local	62
Someswar Valley (1,350 m ad)	Govind	77
	Pant Dhan 6	65
	VL-8	72
	Local	45
Bageswar Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	65
	IR24	72
	Saket 4	60
	Local	48
Chaukhutia Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	78
	IR24	70
	Saket 4	82
	Local	54

^am asl = meters above sea level.

were reared in the laboratory for identification.

The insects appeared in July and remained until October. Infestation peaked from early Aug through late Sep. Average leaf damage was 45-86%. High-yielding dwarf varieties suffered more damage than local tall varieties (see table). Such a high LF incidence in the region's irrigated transplanted rice had not been recorded for 15-20 yr.

The Department of Plant Protection and Agriculture organized a campaign to control LF in infested areas. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC and monocrotophos 40 EC sprayed at 0.5 liter ai/ha gave effective control. □

Assessing the prevalence of rice pests in Cambodia

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Current information on the prevalence of insects and diseases in Cambodia is scanty. In 1990, the Cambodia-IRRI Rice Project sponsored in Phnom Penh a training course on problem diagnosis in rice. After the course, the 90 participants collected insect and disease baseline data in 261 fields in 12 provinces.

Using a zigzag sampling pattern, they examined 15 hills/field. For each hill,

they assessed disease severity (%) and insect injury (%) and estimated insect number by sweepnet. Prevalence was calculated as the proportion of fields in which specific diseases, insects, or beneficial arthropods were found, expressed as a percentage of the total number of fields visited. All fields were visited once from tillering to milk grain stage, and 102 fields were visited a second time from booting to ripening. The stage at which observations were made could not be standardized because of asynchronous planting and the difficulty of visiting fields.

Nearly 80% of the fields sampled were planted to traditional rice varieties, the most common being Phka Khney (8.0% of fields). IR36 and IR42 were the dominant modern varieties, respectively occupying 10.3 and 7.6% of the surveyed fields.

Brown spot (BS) was the most prevalent disease followed by narrow brown spot (Table 1). BS incidence, based on the number of infected tillers, was high in all provinces and in all varieties throughout the crop growth stages. BS was severe in variety Chhmar Prom during the first observation. The widespread occurrence and high incidence of BS may be due to poor plant nutrition, which is a

predisposing factor for the disease.

In most provinces, green leafhoppers (GLH) and brown planthoppers (BPH) were most prevalent during the first observation, followed by spiders and beetles (Table 2). In Takeo and Kompong Speu Provinces, there were more GLH on Phka Khney and IR50 varieties and at tillering to booting stages; more BPH were seen in Svay Rieng Province and on traditional varieties. Spiders and beetles were present throughout crop growth, but in low numbers.

Damage caused by hispa, cutworms, rice gall midge (GM), rice leaffolder, and stemborers was common in most provinces (Table 2). GM damage generally declined from tillering to milk grain stage in contrast to that of hispa, which gradually increased from tillering to flowering in the first observation. Percent insect damage generally increased with growth stage in the second observation, but in general, the insect population and damage were lower in the second observation than in the first observation.

We reported only pest prevalence and not incidence or severity of pest attack because we could not calibrate the

Table 1. Prevalence of rice diseases in provinces of Cambodia, 1990 wet season.

Province	Fields (no.)	Prevalence (% of fields)						
		Brown spot	Narrow brown spot	Bacterial blight	Bacterial leaf streak	Leaf blight	Leaf scald	Sheath blight
<i>First observation</i>								
Banteay Meanchey	10	50.0	20.0	30.0	20.0	60.0	0.0	10.0
Battambang	15	80.0	13.3	6.1	0.0	33.3	0.0	0.0
Kandal	76	34.2	1.3	10.5	10.5	1.3	2.6	0.0
Kompong Cham	10	100.0	20.0	40.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	9	88.9	22.2	0.0	11.1	11.1	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	16	100.0	6.2	0.0	6.2	6.2	0.0	0.0
Kompong Thorn	10	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	41	92.7	24.4	2.4	12.2	9.8	0.0	9.8
Prey Veng	11	63.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Pursat	3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	15	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	45	84.4	20.0	6.7	2.2	11.1	0.0	0.0
<i>Second observation</i>								
Battambang	9	88.9	55.5	11.1	0.0	22.2	0.0	0.0
Kandal	15	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Cham	5	100.0	20.0	80.0	40.0	40.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	2	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	13	38.5	30.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	10	90.0	50.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Prey Veng	5	100.0	60.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	6	83.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	20	100.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0